

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS IN THE EAST OKU REGIONAL GOVERNMENT

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Abstract: Human resources are the main actors in every organization. The success of a company is highly dependent on the human aspect. The human aspect is the main concern of the management control system in a company. Professional human resources are human resources who are reliable and capable in completing the tasks assigned by the company, this must be accompanied by good facilities and motivation. For this reason, this study was made to analyze employee job satisfaction in the work environment of the East OKU regional government. This research uses the method *Explanatory Survey Method*. From this research, it can be concluded that the variables of work culture and work motivation have good results. This shows that with the existence of a good work culture variable, it can build good and measurable performance in an organization, while good work motivation can stimulate human desire or willingness to complete work.

Keywords: Environment, HRD, Motivation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Humans who have reason and instincts as well as a social spirit play an important role in a job, humans have very potential strengths and are often called human resources or human resources, reliable human resources can and are able to manage themselves to achieve prosperity and balance in life. . Human resources are one of the most important elements in an organization, so one of the preparations to face changes in the future is to prepare quality human resources.

Human resources are the main actors in every organization. The success of a company is highly dependent on the human aspect. The human aspect is the main concern of the management control system in a company. Without human resources, the organization will not exist because human resources are assets for organizations or institutions and companies. Professional human resources are human resources who are reliable and capable in completing the tasks assigned by the company.

Each individual has a different role and intelligence in solving problems or tasks. From these differences, both the beliefs and attitudes of employees. These differences are a challenge for companies in dealing with the status of their employees. In addition, in reality many employees often experience several conditions that are not in accordance with what is expected in the scope of their work. If the facilities and task guidance are not in line with the needs and abilities, the employee will experience a decrease in the quality of his work.

Performance quality is a very important factor in every company. There are several factors that must be considered in improving the quality of performance, one of which is the state of the work environment that is useful as a driver of individual behavior to meet their daily needs. To improve the quality of performance, it is necessary to arrange the work

environment as comfortable as possible. A pleasant work environment for employees who are at work will have a positive impact on employees, so that employee performance can increase. The work environment is all workplace conditions that can affect employees either directly or indirectly, besides that the work environment is a human community gathered in a diversity and in changing situations and conditions that can affect employee performance so that the resulting product is less effective and less effective. This means that employee productivity is decreasing.

In principle, the state of the work environment must be properly and fairly for the performance or services of the employees of the company in achieving a goal. The work environment can be used as an important thing for employees where every employee has the right to it. The work environment is one of the sensitive things in the world of work because it can make employees feel satisfied working in the company which will have an impact on employees in improving the quality of employee services.

In addition to the influence of the work environment that can affect the quality of employee service is motivation for employees. Motivation is very influential to maximize employee service quality. Motivation will encourage a person's behavior to perform a certain activity. To get the human resources expected by the company to contribute positively to all company activities in achieving its goals, each employee is expected to have high work motivation so that later it will improve high service quality.

The organizational environment is very important to make a positive contribution to the achievement of organizational goals. Because with a conducive organizational environment, someone will have a high spirit in carrying out the tasks assigned to him. Without pressure, an employee cannot fulfill his duties according to standards or even exceed standards because his motives and motivations in working are not fulfilled. Organizational environment is a work situation that comes from the outside related to the level, direction and persistence of the consistency of the effort that a person makes at work. The problems that exist in the East OKU Regional Government are the employee motivation that occurs at the East OKU Regional Government Office is not optimal, the Employee Work Culture at the East OKU Regional Government Office is not yet optimal, The occurrence of a decrease in employee performance at the East OKU Regional Government Office, The functional management of resource development has not been implemented. human resources at the East OKU Regional Government Office in providing guidance and control of its employees in the direction of performance progress

From this background, a problem formulation can be drawn, namely, how are the conditions of the work environment at the East OKU regional government and what aspects support the performance of the East OKU Regional Government, and how the work environment should be at the East OKU Regional Government Office.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted at the East OKU Regional Government Office (PEMDA). This research is expected to provide input and benefits in improving work culture and motivation on employee performance in the East OKU Regional Government in the future.

The sample in this study were employees of the East OKU Regional Government who had positions at the lower managerial level with a tenure of more than 15 years as many as 25 people.

2.1 Research Variables

The variables contained in this study are:

1. Independent Variable (X)

The independent variable (independent) is a variable that affects other variables. In this research, the independent variables are work culture (X1) and motivation (X2).

2. Dependent Variable

The dependent variable (dependent) is a variable that is influenced by other variables. In this study the dependent variable is performance (Y).

2.2 Operational Variables

1. Motivation is an impulse that causes, moves employees to do work and fulfill their needs. Motivation indicators are:

- a. Income
 - b. Award
 - c. Career Development
 - d. Guidance
2. Work Culture is an employee's attitude towards work and employee behavior at work. The indicators of work culture are:
- a. Employee attitudes and behavior
 - b. Vision, mission and goals of the organization
 - c. Organizational habits
3. Performance is doing work more actively, so that work can be expected to be faster and better and there is a deep pleasure in the work being done. Performance indicators are:
- a. Work relationship
 - b. Job satisfaction
 - c. Work climate

The indicators of each of the variables above are used as the basis for compiling a list of questions distributed to respondents. The data collected through the questionnaire is qualitative data which is then converted into quantitative data by scoring each alternative answer as follows:

Furthermore, before the measuring instrument is given to the respondents, the questionnaire needs to be tested outside the sample to determine the validity and reliability. The validity and reliability for the questionnaire test.

2.3. Data collection

Research instrument is a tool used to make measurements, in this case a tool to collect data in a study. Therefore, a measuring instrument must be used. The measuring instrument is often referred to as a research instrument (Siswoyo, 2004: 191)

For data collection this research was carried out with a qualitative assessment approach. The instrument used to measure the variables was developed with a Likert scale. This scale with five levels of alternative answers, namely categories:

1. Strongly Agree (SS) : Score 5
2. Agree (S) : Score 4
3. Disagree (KS) : Score 3
4. Disagree (TS) : Score 2
5. Strongly Disagree (STS): Score 1

The instrument is used to assess the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group about social phenomena. In this study, the dimensions to measure the variables that have been determined are determined, namely indicators of work culture, work motivation and employee performance. Then this indicator is used as a starting point for compiling instrument items in the form of closed questions, Sugiyono (2004;97), the answers to each item have a level from very positive to very negative. The questions asked are to obtain primary data.

The questions raised are qualitative in nature, for the purposes of analyzing the data that has been collected is converted into quantitative data. This data collection is adjusted to the nature of the statements in the questionnaire items.

2.4. Test Instrument

- a. Validity test

According to Siswoyo (2008:1) validity determines the extent to which a measuring instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. To measure the validity of the three instruments (work culture, motivation and employee performance). The instrument was tested using 25 employees as respondents. The instrument validity of the three variables was assessed by calculating the data using the Pearson Product Moment formula in the SPSS program. The statement/question item is declared valid if the Pearson Product Moment value $> r$ Table marked with (*) and (**). The critical number of table correlation (Table r) is 0.361. This figure is obtained from the r -product moment table at a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) and $N = 25$ (according to the number of respondents). Thus, if there is a correlation coefficient of the question/statement item below 0.361, it is declared invalid. Test the validity of the instrument dependent variable (Dependent), namely employee performance (Y) and the independent variable (Independent), namely Work Culture (X1) and Work Motivation (X2), the following results were obtained:

b. Reliability Test

If the measuring instrument is valid, then the reliability of the measuring instrument is tested. reliability is a value that indicates the consistency of a measuring instrument in measuring the same symptoms. The instrument is declared reliable if Cronbach Alpha > 0.6 .

The smaller the measurement error, the more reliable the measuring instrument and vice versa, the greater the measurement error, the less reliable the measuring instrument. Several measurement errors can be identified and the correlation between the results of the first, second and third measurements can be assessed. When the correlation value (r) is squared, the result is called the Coefficient of Determination, which shows an indication of the size of the actual measurement results. The higher the correlation number, the greater the value of the coefficient of determination and the lower the measurement error.

The instrument reliability test that has been carried out for the variables of work culture, motivation and employee performance using the SPSS program obtained the following results:

1. Employee Work Culture Variable Instrument (X1)

From the tests carried out for the work culture instrument (X1) of 11 questions that were tested for reliability, it was found that the Cronbach Alpha value was 0.687, this alpha value was good because it was above the value of 0.6 on the Cronbach Alpha value, and it can be concluded that the instrument variable work culture (X1) is reliable.

2. Employee Work Motivation Variable Instrument (X2)

From the trials carried out for the work motivation instrument (X2) of 11 questions that were carried out the reliability test obtained a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.669, this alpha value was good because it was at a value of 0.6 on the Cronbach Alpha value, and it can be concluded that the instrument variable motivation (X2) is reliable.

3. Employee Performance variable instrument (Y)

From the trials carried out for the Performance instrument (Y) of 12 questions that were tested for reliability, it was found that the Cronbach Alpha value was 0.772, this alpha value was good because it was above the value of 0.6 on the Cronbach Alpha value, and it can be concluded that the performance variable instrument employee (Y) is not reliable.

3. RESULT

3.1. Analysis

This analysis is carried out by analyzing the Liker scale table by making the frequency distribution of the results of the study into a table and then interpreting it. Based on the results of research and calculations carried out, the respondents' answers to questions asked about work culture and motivation with employee performance at the East OKU Regional Government Office were described based on the indicators used.

This section describes the research data obtained in the field to get an overview of some of the characteristics of each variable studied, both data on independent variables consisting of Work Culture (X1) and Motivation (X2) and the dependent variable Employee Performance (Y). . The data was obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire distributed to 25 respondents using an instrument developed and made by the researcher himself. The characteristics in

question are the distribution of variable scores which are manifested in the form of the average value, mode, median, standard deviation and variance. However, previously in this chapter, the analysis requirements test will be carried out, namely the normality test, homogeneity test and linearity test as a condition for testing the proposed hypothesis. Then at the end of the hypothesis testing, followed by a discussion of the results of the study.

1. Description of Work Culture Variable (X1)

a. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

From the results of the analysis of the answers given by 25 respondents who became the research sample, descriptive statistics were obtained regarding work culture as follows:

Table. 1: Descriptive Statistical Data of Work Culture Variable(X1)

		Work Culture
N	Valid	25
	Missing	0
mean		43.16
Std. Error of Mean		.621
median		43.00
Mode		41 ^a
Std. Deviation		3.105
Variance		9,640
Skewness		.319
Std. Error of Skewness		.464
Kurtosis		.622
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.902
Range		14
Minimum		37
Maximum		51
Sum		1079

From the table above, it can be explained that N or the number of valid data (legitimate to be processed) is 25 data, while the missing data is zero. This means that all data is ready to be processed. The mean or average work culture score is 43.16 with a standard error of 0.621. The use of Standard error of mean is to estimate the size of the population mean estimated from the sample. For this reason, with a certain standard error of mean and at a 95% confidence level, the average work culture population score becomes $\pm 43.16 (2 \times 0.621) = 41.92$ to 44.40. The median is the midpoint of the data if all the data is sorted and divided by two equally. The median score of 43.00 indicates that 50% of work culture scores are 43.00 and above and 50% are 43.00 and below. The standard deviation is 3.105 and the variance which is a multiple of the standard deviation is to determine the level of spread of the data to the average. For this reason, with a certain standard deviation and at a 95% confidence level, the distribution of the employee culture population data on the average is: $43.16 \pm (2 \times 3.105) = 23.88$ to 62.44. The Skewness measure is 0.319. for the analysis, it is converted to a number of skewness ratios or in this case the skewness ratio = $0.319/0.464 = 0.687$ as a guideline if the skewness ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. Kurtosis size is 0.622 for analysis converted into kurtosis ratio numbers or in this case kurtosis ratio = $0.622/0.902 = 0.689$ as a guideline if the kurtosis ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. While the Range is the maximum and minimum values. The maximum value is 51 and the minimum value is h 37 so that the range is 14. And Sum is the sum of all processed data, which is 1079. To find out the frequency histogram of the score can be seen in the picture. 3

Figure 1: Histogram of Work Culture Score Frequency

From Figure 1 above, it is revealed that the distribution of employee culture variables is normal because the curve is symmetrical. This indicates that the work culture of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office is categorized as moderate or good.

Table. 2: Items of Work Culture Instrument (X1)

No.	Question / Statement	Total Value	Score Average
1.	The smoothness of the task depends on the attitude and behavior of employees at work	90	3.6
2.	Get sanctions for employees who violate the rules and regulations	104	4.16
3.	Employees must obey the rules and norms of the organization in order to create harmony in work among fellow employees	99	3.96
4.	Employees must have a work spirit based on the vision and mission of the organization	97	3.88
5.	Employees must work in accordance with organizational goals	91	3.64
6.	A good employee must do the job without being forced	103	4.12
7.	The formation of good habits in the organization starts from the boss	99	3.96
8.	Organizational habits must always be applied well within the organization	97	3.88
9.	Good habits are the beginning of good employee performance	101	4.04
10.	Employee work effectiveness is useful in obtaining better results	96	3.84
11.	The need to maintain a comfortable work environment for all employees and leaders	102	4.08
Average value		1079	4.11

Based on the data from the average value of the Work Culture variable indicator (X1) above, it can be said that the work culture at the East OKU Regional Government Office of all indicators made questions / statements which include; 1.) Attitudes and behavior of employees 2.) Vision, Mission and Organizational Goals 3.) Internal habits of the organization, showing a good average score of 4.11.

Based on the item analysis of the work culture variable instrument above, there are no indicators of work culture that are not optimal or are in the interval $2 < 3$ (good enough category).

While all indicators of employee work culture are in the very good category, namely at intervals of $4 < 5$ so that it is a strength to maintain the work culture of the East OKU Regional Government Office.

Overall, the indicators of the work culture of the East OKU Regional Government Office have reached the very good category, so that it is a strength for optimal performance of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office.

2. Description of Motivation Variable (X2)

a. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

From the results of the analysis of the answers given by 25 respondents who became the research sample, descriptive statistics were obtained regarding work motivation as follows:

Table. 3: Descriptive Statistical Data Motivation Variable (X2)

		Motivation
N	Valid	25
	Missing	0
mean		43.24
Std. Error of Mean		.572
median		43.00
Mode		43
Std. Deviation		2.862
Variance		8.190
Skewness		-.807
Std. Error of Skewness		.464
Kurtosis		.753
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.902
Range		12
Minimum		36
Maximum		48
Sum		1081
Percentiles	10	38.60
	90	47.00

From the table above, it can be explained that N or the number of valid data (legitimate to be processed) is 25 data, while the missing data is zero. This means that all data is ready to be processed. The mean or average work culture score is 43.24 with an error standard of Mean 0.572. The use of Standard error of mean is to estimate the size of the population mean estimated from the sample. For this reason, with a certain standard error of mean and at a 95% confidence level, the average population score of work motivation becomes $\pm 43.24 (2 \times 0.572) = 42.096$ to 44.384 . The median is the midpoint of the data if all the data is sorted and divided by two equally. The median score of 43.00 indicates that 50% of work motivation scores are 43.00 and above and 50% are 43.00 and below. The standard deviation is 2.862 and the variance which is a multiple of the standard deviation is 8.190 to determine the level of spread of the data to the average. For this reason, with a certain standard deviation and at a 95% confidence level, the distribution of population data on employee work motivation on the average is: $43.24 \pm (2 \times 2.862) = 37.516$ to 48.964 . Skewness size is 0.807. for analysis, it is converted to a number of skewness ratios or in this case the skewness ratio = $0.807/0.464 = 1.739$ as a guide if the skewness ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. Kurtosis size is 0.753 for analysis converted into kurtosis ratio numbers or in this case kurtosis ratio = $0.753/0.902 = 0.834$ as a guide if the kurtosis ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. Range is the maximum and minimum values. The maximum value is 48 and the minimum value is 36 so that the range is 12. Sum is the sum of all processed data, which is 1081. To find out the frequency histogram of the score can be seen in the picture. 3

Figure 2: Histogram of Motivation Score Frequency

From Figure 2 above, it is revealed that the distribution of the employee motivation variable is normal because the curve is symmetrical. This indicates that the work motivation of employees at the East OKU Regional Government Office is categorized as moderate or good.

Table. 4: Work Motivation Instrument Items (X 2)

No.	Question / Statement	Total Value	Score Average
1.	To get a large income, employees must work hard	95	3.8
2.	Leaders provide additional incentives for employees who do well	98	3.92
3.	Employees work hard to increase their income and provide for their families	96	3.84
4.	High income is the main goal of employees working	108	4.32
5.	Employees work hard just to get rewards	99	3.96
6.	Awards are given only to outstanding employees	100	4
7.	All employees have high hopes for career development	101	4.04
8.	Career development is important for employees	97	3.88
9.	Guidance must always be given intensively to employees	93	3.72
10.	Guidance can be obtained from superiors and coworkers	94	3.76
11.	Without the guidance of employees can not work well	100	4
Average value		1081	4.00

Based on the data from the average value of the work motivation variable indicator (X2) above, it can be said that work motivation at the East OKU Regional Government Office of all indicators made questions / statements which include; 1.) Income 2.) Awards 3. Career Development 4. Guidance, showing a good average score of 4.00. Based on the item analysis of the work motivation variable instrument above, there are no indicators of work motivation that are not optimal or are in the interval $2 < 3$ (good enough category). While all indicators of employee work motivation are in the very good category, namely at intervals of $4 < 5$ so that it is a strength to maintain work motivation at the East OKU Regional Government Office. Overall indicators of work motivation of the East OKU Regional Government Office have reached the very good category, so that it is a strength for optimal performance of the East OKU Regional Government Office employees.

3. Description of Employee Performance Variables

a. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

From the results of the analysis of the answers given by 25 respondents who became the research sample, descriptive statistical data regarding employee performance were obtained as follows:

Table. 5: Descriptive Statistics Data Performance Variables (Y)

		Performance
N	Valid	25
	Missing	0
mean		54.52
Std. Error of Mean		.589
median		55.00
Mode		55
Std. Deviation		2,946
Variance		8,677
Skewness		-1.441
Std. Error of Skewness		.464
Kurtosis		1,820
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.902
Range		11
Minimum		47
Maximum		58
Sum		1363
Percentiles	10	48.00
	90	58.00

From the table above, it is explained that N or the number of valid data (legitimate to be processed) is 25 data, while the missing data is zero. This means that all data is ready to be processed. The mean or average performance score is 54.52 with a standard error of 0.589. The use of Standard error of mean is to estimate the size of the population mean estimated from the sample. For this reason, with a certain standard error of mean and at a 95% confidence level, the average population score of performance becomes $\pm 54.52 (2 \times 0.589) = 53.34$ to 55.69. The median is the midpoint of the data if all the data is sorted and divided by two equally. The median score of 55.00 indicates that 50% of the employee performance scores are 55.00 and above and 50% are 55.00 and below. The standard deviation is 2,946 and the variance which is a multiple of the standard deviation is 8,677 to determine the level of spread of the data to the average. For this reason, with a certain standard deviation and at a 95% confidence level, the distribution of population data on employee performance to the average is: $54.52 \pm (2 \times 2.946) = 38.63$ to 50.41. The Skewness measure is 1.441 for the analysis converted to a number of skewness ratios or in this case the skewness ratio = $1.441/0.464 = 3.105$ as a guide if the skewness ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. The size of the kurtosis was 1.820 for the analysis converted into a kurtosis ratio number or in this case the kurtosis ratio = $1.820/0.902 = 2.017$ as a guideline if the kurtosis ratio is between -2 and +2 then the data distribution is normal. Range is the maximum and minimum values. The maximum value is 58 and the minimum value is 47 so that the range is 11. Sum is the sum of all processed data, which is 1363. To find out the histogram of the score frequency can be seen in the picture. 3

Figure 3: Histogram of Employee Performance Score Frequency

From Figure 3 above, it is revealed that the distribution of employee performance variables is normal because the curve is symmetrical. This indicates that the performance of employees at the East OKU Regional Government Office is categorized as moderate or good.

Table. 6: Employee Performance Instrument Items (Y)

No.	Question / Statement	Total Value	Score Average
1.	Employees must arrange the stages of work activities before starting work	115	4.6
2.	The importance of the ability of employees to carry out work according to the schedule of activities prepared	94	3.76
3.	Employees must understand the stages of work before starting	114	4.56
4.	Employees must understand the technical requirements of the job at work	115	4.6
5.	Employees must be able to increase work creativity	115	4.6
6.	Work facilities and infrastructure really support the smooth running of the organization's activities	120	4.8
7.	Employees want comfort at work	114	4.56
8.	Between employees must have good cooperation	114	4.56
9.	Provide input with other employees	114	4.56
10.	The need for work guidelines for employees at work	112	4.48
11.	The need for regular meetings to discuss work programs	117	4.68
12.	Employee discipline is very influential on employee performance	119	4.76
Average value		1363	4.59

Based on the data from the average value of the employee performance variable indicator (Y) above, it can be said that the performance at the East OKU Regional Government Office of all indicators made questions / statements which include; 1. Work relationship, 2. Job satisfaction, 3. Work climate, showing a good average score of 4.59

Based on the item analysis of the employee performance variable instrument above, there are no performance indicators that are not optimal or are in the interval $2 < 3$ (good enough category).

While all employee performance indicators are in the very good category, namely at intervals of $4 < 5$ so that it is a strength to maintain the performance of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office.

Overall, the performance indicators of employees at the East OKU Regional Government Office have reached the very good category, so that it is a strength to realize the optimal and maximum achievement of employee performance at the East OKU Regional Government Office.

4.2. Test Requirements Analysis

The requirements test was carried out on 25 employees as the research sample. The research data is processed with parameterized statistics that work with the assumption that the data for each variable forms a normal, homogeneous and linear distribution. If the data is not normal, homogeneous and linear, then parametric statistics cannot be used as an analytical tool so it is necessary to test for normality, homogeneity and linearity.

1. Normality Test

Normality test was carried out with each independent variable to determine whether the two populations were normally distributed or not. Testing this requirement is done using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test from SPSS, the normality of the data distribution can be calculated based on the Asymptotic Significance value.

The test criteria is that H_0 is rejected if the Asymptotic Significance is smaller than . H_0 states a normal distribution, while the significance level used as the basis for rejecting or accepting decisions with normal or not distribution of data is with a level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The results of the normality test with the SPSS program are presented in the following table:

Table. 7: Normality Test Results of the Three Variables

		Work Culture	Motivation	Performance
N		25	25	25
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	mean	43.16	43.24	54.52
	Std. Deviation	3.105	2.862	2,946
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.100	.267	.230
	Positive	.100	.115	.119
	negative	-.083	-.267	-.230
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.501	1.333	1.150
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.963	.057	.142

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

From the results of the normality test, the Asymp value is obtained. Sig for the work culture variable (X1) is 0.963, for the work motivation variable (X2), the value is 0.057 and the employee performance variable is 0.142. Asymp Value. The third sig of the variables shows a number greater than = 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data on the variables of work culture, work motivation, and employee performance are normally distributed. Thus, hypothesis testing using correlation and regression analysis can be carried out.

2. Homogeneity Test

The homogeneity test in question is to test the homogeneity of variance between groups of Y data which is developed based on the similarity of X values. This requirement is carried out using the Chi-Square Test from the SPSS program.

The test criteria are to accept H0 if the significant level is greater than and reject H0 if the Asymptotic Significance is less than . H0 states that the distribution of data is homogeneous, while the significance level used as the basis for rejecting or accepting decisions with homogeneous or not the distribution of data is with a level of = 0.05. Homogeneity test results with the program are presented in the following table;

Table. 8: Homogeneity Test Results

	Work Culture	Motivation	Performance
Chi-Square	6,240 ^a	18,600 ^b	6,680 ^c
df	10	9	7
asymp. Sig.	.795	.092	.463

a. 11 cells (100.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 2.3.

b. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 2.5.

c. 8 cells (100.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 3.1.

From the test results obtained the Asymp value. Sig for the work culture variable (X1) is 0.795, for the motivation variable (X2) the value is 0.092 while the employee performance variable (Y) is 0.463. Asymp Value. The third sig of the variables shows a number greater than = 0.05, it can be concluded that the data on the variables of work culture, motivation and employee performance are homogeneous. Thus, hypothesis testing using regression analysis can be carried out.

3. Linearity Test

The use of statistical regression analysis techniques to test the effect between variables must meet the requirements, among others, that these variables must be linear. If this trait is not affected, then the regression and effect analysis technique cannot be performed using one-way ANOVA with a significance rate of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

a. Linearity Test of the Effect of Work Culture (X1) on Performance (Y)

Based on the results of the linearity test calculation using the SPSS program (in appendix 17) for the work culture variable (X1) on employee performance (Y), the sig deviation from linearity value is $0.153 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the influence of work culture (X1) on performance employee (Y) Linear.

b. Linearity Test of the Effect of Motivation (X2) and Employee Performance (Y)

Based on the results of the linearity test calculation (in Appendix 17) for the motivation variable (X2) on employee performance (Y), the sig deviation from linearity value is $0.473 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the influence between motivation (X2) on employee performance (Y) is linear.

4. CONCLUSION

There is a positive and significant influence between Work Culture (X1) and Work Motivation (X2) together on the performance of employees (Y) of the East OKU Regional Government Office. This is confirmed from the analysis of the coefficient of determination (Adjusted Rsquare) the influence of work culture and motivation on employee performance at the East OKU Regional Government Office of 0.254, which means that employee performance can be explained by the variables of work culture and motivation together of 25.4%.

There is a positive and significant influence between work culture (X1) on employee performance (Y) East OKU Regional Government Office. This is confirmed from the analysis of the coefficient of determination (Adjusted Rsquare) the influence of work culture on the performance of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office of 0.250 which means that employee performance can be explained by the work culture variable of 25%

There is a positive and significant influence between work motivation (X2) on employee performance (Y) East OKU Regional Government Office. This is confirmed from the analysis of the coefficient of determination (Adjusted Rsquare) the effect of motivation on the performance of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office of 0.174 which means that employee performance can be explained by the work culture variable of 17.4%

Partially, the work culture variable has a more dominant influence on the performance of the employees of the East OKU Regional Government Office compared to the work motivation variable. So that to realize optimal employee performance, the first to be improved and improved is the work motivation variable.

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